

**FORMATION AND PRINCIPLE OF PEDAGOGICAL ETHICS IN
FUTURE PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS**

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Abstract: The article talks about the pedagogical factors of the formation of pedagogical ethics culture in the future teaching staff and their analysis.

Key words: pedagogue, culture, "Deontology", pedagogical ethics, culture,

Choosing an innovative way of development, creating and implementing high technologies, the growing role of knowledge and information in the socio-economic development of the country puts a great demand on highly qualified specialists. This requires new forms of integration of education, science and production, and sets the formation of a new generation of pedagogues capable of training competitive specialists as one of the priorities. Modernization of higher educational institutions and the educational process in them, improvement of the quality of the system of training of pedagogues, equipping future primary school teachers with modern professional competencies, formation of acmeological motivation in relation to professional activity in the process of developing the pedagogical skills of pedagogues is considered one of the important tasks. A pedagogue plays a special role in the formation of pedagogical ethics skills in future elementary school teachers. In this process, the role of the "educator" is to create an

atmosphere of creativity in the audience. However, the pedagogue should create an environment in the group where the future elementary school teachers can feel free and share their thoughts and ideas. In order to further activate the processes taking place in the human mind, future elementary school teachers should act freely in asking different questions, departing from the established rules and regulations. The correct attitude towards their ideas is important in their understanding of the possible and impossible conditions. provides.

Pedagogical ethics culture is a set of general moral rules necessary in the process of the teacher's relationship with students, the pedagogue's manners based on normative and moral views. It is known that the work of a teacher-educator on the formation of the spiritual-ethical, especially pedagogical image of teachers is complex and multifaceted. Pedagogical ethics helps to create multifaceted relationships and problems, provides self-awareness and self-improvement by taking advantage of pedagogical experiences created by culture. F.N. Gonobolin, N.V. Kozmin, A.I. Sherbakov, A.A. Slastenin and others have conducted research on pedagogical ethics and cultural issues. The work of a teacher-educator on the formation of a spiritual-ethical, in particular, pedagogical image is complex and multifaceted. Pedagogical ethics helps to create multifaceted relationships and problems, provides self-awareness and self-improvement by taking advantage of pedagogical experiences created by culture. F.N. Gonobolin, N.V. Kozmin, A.I. Sherbakov, A.A. Slastenin and others have conducted research on pedagogical ethics and cultural issues. through his interests, ability, confidence, and ideas, a pedagogue will consist of a solid set of reasons aimed at humanizing activity.

The personal professional pedagogical direction of the teacher in organizing the pedagogical process includes the following. Ideas (a broad view of pedagogical tasks, pedagogical thinking, development, self-development, achieving professionalism in pedagogical interactions) Interests (interest in science, improvement of psychological and pedagogical knowledge, teachers' training raising the level of education and general spiritual culture) Valuable directions (acquiring higher knowledge, educating, activating students in the teacher and development processes) Reasons and goals are based on the talent for pedagogical activity. The reasons are expressed by the pedagogue's conscious pursuit of pedagogical activity

CONCLUSION

Thus, in order to be the owner of pedagogical skills, a teacher should know his subject based on the requirements of the time, have pedagogical and psychological knowledge, and should have humanity, inquisitiveness and selflessness.

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